

Statistical Modelling of Pandemic-Survival Social Variables and Electronic Banking in Deposit Money Banks in Rivers State (2020-2023)

Onwurike, God'slove Chukwuemeka, Wonu, Nduka and Victor-Edem, U. A.

onuobinekehenry@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

The study presented the statistical modelling of pandemic-survival social variables and electronic banking in deposit money banks in Rivers State. The electronic banking was measured by the internet banking and the mobile banking, while some pandemic-survival social variables such as perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, social influence, service quality and support (Hedonic motivation) were obtained using questionnaire. Descriptive statistics and multiple linear regression were applied. The study revealed that all the pandemic-survival social variables had positive impact on the electronic banking in Nigeria. The hedonic motivation was found to be more significant with the value of 0.000, while, service quality was found to be insignificant with the value of 0.837. The multiple linear regression model was found to be significant with significant level of 0.000 and with the coefficient of determination value of 75.2%. This showed that the model was able to explain the variation in the system by over 75%. The study among other things recommended that banks should be established in rural communities to enable the primitive once have knowledge of some banking innovations.

Keyword: Pandemic-survivor, electronic banking, social variables, statistical modeling.

1. Introduction

The arrival of the Internet not only propelled the growth and development of new industries but also changed the business plans and operations of many others, including the banking sector (Hernández-Murillo, 2010). Also, the ever-increasing competition and increasingly demanding customers in the financial institution space have led to the development of alternate delivery channels for banking services. One of the delivery channels introduced is online banking (Ololade & Ogbeide, 2017). Online banking is referred to as electronic banking and electronic banking is otherwise known as e-banking. Compared to other developed nations like the United States and the United Kingdom, Nigeria, a developing country, did not embrace e-banking early enough. Nigeria adopted the e-banking system in the early 2000s (Onodugo et al. 2015) Before the rise of e-banking in Nigeria, transactions were carried out manually, i.e. with the intervention of human handlers. This process resulted in delays and a high rate of transaction inaccuracy due to human error.

The total number of deposit money banks in Nigeria that have the right for their customers to carry out e-banking activities are thirty-three. The ability of these banks to satisfy and retain their customers in this era will depend mainly on the development and maintenance of their information technology infrastructure. Nigerian banks have invested much in technology to catch up with global developments and improve the quality of their service delivery. They have widely adopted electronic and telecommunication networks for delivering a wide range of value-added products

and solutions to their users (Chiemeké, & Evwiekpaefe, 2006). These vast advances in Internet technology have brought about a significant shift in banking operations. This, in effect, has resulted in the adoption of e-banking by banks. With the aid of e-banking, banks can work effectively and achieve high profits. The dominant driving forces of e-banking among customers include but are not limited to better access to services, reduction of transaction delays, decongestion of long queues in the banking hall and higher privacy etc. With e-banking, customers can carry out related transactions from the comfort of their homes and offices anywhere and anytime. Based on ever-evolving new innovative technologies, these solutions provided by the banks mean that consumers or users should have the required skills to use them. It is worthy of note that e-banking also coexists with traditional banking methods, i.e. bank branches and telephone banking.

Electronic Banking

Electronic banking can be described as using the internet as a distribution mode for the provision of banking services like electronic bill payment, opening a deposit account, online money transfers, and online cash withdrawals.

Social Influence

This involves the efforts made to change another person's belief, behaviour or attitude, which may be intentionally or unintentionally.

Types of Social Influence

Kelman, (1958) describes three levels of the depth of social influence and they include the following; Compliance, Identification and Internalisation.

Compliance

This describes the lowest level of social influence. It occurs when a person does what is actually expected of him or her to do. That is to say, the person does the expected thing in the public but holds different views in private.

Identification

This appears to be the medium level of social influence, which comes to play when an individual identifies with the group just because they he has value for that group and want to join the group. That individual might change some of his or her behaviours in public and also in private but might not agree with all aspects of the group's believe.

Internalisation

This appears to be the deepest level social influence whereby the individual has completely taken on the expectations of the group, in private as well as in public. This change continues indefinitely even in the absence of the group. It is also known as conformity. These social influences identified above will be broadly discussed under the following; perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, service quality, support, price value, hedonic motivation and risk.

The practice of Electronic Banking otherwise known as E-Banking in Nigeria have not gained the desired attention in the literature. The government will always talk about cashless policy which is aimed at reducing the circulation of the Nigeria Naira to among other things reduce crime, such as kidnappings, money laundering and also, increasing the value of our local currency (naira). The

government being aware of the level of help this monetary policy will bring to the citizenry, if implemented to the latter have not made time to create needed awareness of this policy to the ordinary Nigerian, to enable all to carry out the E-Banking with little or no supervision. The E-Banking as it were, would have been a major way to reduce the spread of COVID 19 or any other pandemic if the people had been sensitized about it always. There are some important pandemic-survival social variables that would have contributed meaningfully on the E-Banking especially during any pandemic, such as; perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, social influence, service quality and support, price value, hedonic motivation and risk. These were as observed in the last COVID 19 era. This study seeks to examine the effect of these pandemic-survival social variables on E-Banking such as Mobile App and Internet Banking during future occurrence of any pandemic in Nigeria. The study covered the period between 2020-2023 and proper recommendation will be made to guide the populace on how best be safe during this period.

Hosein (2009) explained that e-banking is an internet portal through which customers can use different banking services, adding that banks' websites which provide only information on their pages without the option to initiate transactions are not qualified as banks offering e-banking services. Nitsure (2003) defined e-banking as the provision of banking products and services through electronic delivery channels. Festus & Amaechi (2014) described e-banking as the provision of banking services to customers through the internet, adding that services offered by banks using the internet include: mobile banking (m-banking), internet banking (IB), automated teller machine (ATM), fund transfers, e-payments etc. The term e-banking also refers to how consumers, with the aid of the Internet, access their bank accounts and initiate banking transactions (Keivani et al., 2012). For simplicity, this definition is adopted in this study. In the end, the customer determines whether they will use e-banking based on the needs they have for it. Customers are more likely to accept a particular service if it clearly illustrates the benefits and how it meets their needs (Hosein, 2009). Davis (1986) introduced one of the commonly used frameworks as shown in figure 1 to study the acceptance of information systems known as the technology acceptance model (TAM). Predictions about the use of an information system were made using this model. This intention-based model aims to explain why users accept or reject a given technology by suggesting that when users are presented with new technology, several factors influence their decision about how and when they will use it (Ammenwerth, 2019; Lala, 2014). The main constructs of TAM are perceived ease of use (PEOU) and perceived usefulness (PU). The model proves that the actual use of a system is influenced by behavioural intention to use (BI) which in turn is jointly determined by the attitude of an individual toward using the system and PU (Davis et al., 1989); which means that when a system delivers the expected outcome, attitude, BI and actual use increase. Attitude is directly determined by two important factors; PEOU and PU (El-Qireem, 2013; Hosein, 2009). PU refers to the degree to which an individual believes that using a particular system would enhance his or her job performance (Davis, 1986) while, PEOU is defined as an individual's expectation that a particular system is simple to use (Ammenwerth, 2019). Acceptance is commonly understood as BI, and BI is the measure of an individual's readiness to perform a particular action (Al-Tarawneh, 2016). BI is the most direct antecedent to IT use and sometimes, in the study of TAM, BI is the only measured outcome as it reliably predicts actual use (Holden & Karsh, 2010).

Several empirical studies have adapted TAM to investigate users' acceptance of e-banking (Abbad, 2013; Ahmad, 2018; Ayo et al., 2016; Chandio, 2008; Mulia et al., 2021; Yousafzai, 2012). Prior research on TAM, has made some modifications and extensions to include constructs such as trust

and compatibility (Fonchamnyo, 2012; Mwiya et al., 2017; Suh & Han, 2002; Yee-Loong Chong et al., 2010). **Covid-19 and e-banking**

Indrasari et al. (2022), examined the “Determinants of satisfaction and loyalty of e-banking users during the covid-19 pandemic” among customers of Indonesia’s local banks and their findings reveal that service reliability, security and privacy of the e-banking platform variable have a significant impact on e-banking user satisfaction in Indonesia. Facilitating conditions, uncertainty and self-efficacy significantly impact e-banking acceptance and, hence, have the potential to increase the acceptance of e-banking services in Oman (Al-Hajri et al., 2022). Bekiris (2022) pointed out that satisfaction with e-banking depends on the technology of e-banking, the cost of services, and the ease of use. The quality of services m-banking applications depends on network connectivity. This means that good network connectivity is equal to the quality of services provided (Salam et al., 2021). Moulton et al. (2020), while examining the factors affecting the use of online banking platforms in Jamaica during the covid-19 discovered that the amount of information, internet connectivity, frequency of use, PU, PEOU, as well as age and employment status have a significant impact on online banking usage. A study on the stimulation of the covid-19 outbreak on the development of e-banking in Iran concluded that a necessity lies in incentive programs to keep customers interested in e-banking (Shahabi et al., 2020), although, for some, the risk component in the transaction has the most important influence on the intention to accept e-banking services, as users pointed out that data privacy and security measures of e-banking technology are the issues of concern ((Ketema, 2020; Nga, 2022), while for others, the website design namely ease of navigation, access, loading time, clarity, accuracy, and readability are of priority (Al-Qeisi & Al-Abdallah, 2014; Ul Haq & Awan, 2020).

2. Materials and Methods

The following methods were applied in this study;

The arithmetic mean of a data set is given as

$$\hat{x} = \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{x_i}{n} \quad (1)$$

If some of the observations were repeated, we talk about frequency and the formula for the arithmetic mean would now be given as

$$\hat{x} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n f_i(x_i)}{\sum_{i=1}^n f_i}$$

Where the f is the frequency.

The standard deviation is given as

$$S.D = \sqrt{\frac{(x_i - \hat{x})^2}{n}} \quad (2)$$

Multiple Regression Analysis

The multiple regression model to be applied is given as

$$EB = \beta_0 + \beta_1 PU + \beta_2 PEU + \beta_3 SI + \beta_4 SQ + \beta_6 PV + \beta_7 HM + \epsilon \quad (3)$$

EB= E-Banking as the response variable, measured by Mobile App and Internet Banking

PU=Perceived usefulness

PEU= Perceived ease of use

SI=Social influence

SQ=Service quality

PV=Price value

HM=Hedonic motivation

and ϵ is the random error.

Multiple Linear Regression Analysis of the pandemic-survival variables on the Electronic Banking

Table 1: Multiple Linear Regression Analysis

Model summary		R	R Square	Adj. R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	
1		.867 ^a	.752	.737	1.57178	
Anova		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	919.304	7	131.329	53.159	.000
	Residual	303.871	123	2.470		
	Total	1223.176	130			
Coefficients		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coeff. Beta	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error			
1	(Constant)	-.438	1.028		-.426	.671
	Perceived usefulness	.201	.078	.201	2.596	.011
	Perceived ease of use	.222	.076	.232	2.933	.004
	Social influence	.188	.066	.167	2.840	.005
	Risk	.030	.066	.024	.455	.650
	Service quality	.016	.077	.011	.206	.837
	Price value	.243	.063	.234	3.839	.000
	Hedonic Motivation	.340	.095	.217	3.593	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Electronic Banking

b. Predictors:(Constant), hedonic motivation, risk, service quality, social influence, price value, perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use

PU, PEU, HM, SQ, S, the usefulness of e-banking, and e-banking usage were the independent factors, and their results were shown in Table 4.7. T-statistics were represented by the numbers in parenthesis.

The estimated model is given as

$$EB = -0.438 + 0.201PU + 0.222PEU + 0.188SI + 0.016SQ + 0.243PV + 0.340HM + \epsilon$$

3. Discussions of Results

Perceived Usefulness of E-banking During the Pandemic

In Table 4.3, it was observed that the item with the strongest response rate was “e-banking made it simple for the participants to carry out financial activities,” with a weighted mean of 4.26 and a standard deviation of 1.19. The participants thought that “using e-banking boosted their productivity,” as indicated by the mean score. Overall, respondents gave the statement, “they found e-banking useful in managing their financial transactions,” a 4.05 (agreed) rating.

This suggests that with social distancing measures in place and many physical bank branches closed or operating on reduced hours, e-banking has provided a convenient alternative for customers to manage their finances. More so, e-banking has allowed financial institutions to continue providing essential financial services to their customers even in areas with strict lockdown measures. With many people unable to leave their homes, online banking has become a lifeline for those who need to access their funds, pay bills, or manage their accounts.

Consistent with a report by McKinsey & Company (2021), the covid-19 outbreak has accelerated the shift towards e-banking, with the number of digital banking users and handlers increasing by up to 20% in some regions. Similarly, the report stresses that banks that have invested in e-channels have been able to better serve their customers during the outbreak and have seen increased customer loyalty as a result. Thus, e-banking has proven to be an invaluable tool during the covid-19 outbreak, providing a safe and convenient way for customers to manage their finances. As the covid-19 continues, it is likely that e-banking will continue to play an essential role in the banking industry and other sectors.

The multiple linear regression revealed that perceived usefulness had positive impact on the electronic banking with the parameter value of 0.201, standard error of 0.078, t-value of 2.596 and significant level of 0.011.

Ease of use of e-banking during the pandemic

Table 4.4 shows that the item with the strongest response rate was that “participants found it easy to use their e-banking application,” with a weighted mean of 4.06 and a standard dev. of 1.17. The participants apparently acknowledged that “learning to use e-banking requires little effort,” as seen in the result of the mean score. Overall, respondents gave the statement that, “it is easy for them to become skilful at using e-banking,” with a 3.95 mean (agreed) rating. This infers that e-financial (digital) services have provided a convenient and safe alternative for customers to manage their finances during covid-19 outbreak times. In accordance with World Bank (2020), there has been a significant increase in the use of digital financial services during the outbreak. Further, World Bank (2020) emphasised that e-banking platforms are relatively easy to use and provide a safe and convenient way for customers to conduct their transactions.

The linear regression revealed that the perceived ease of use had positive impact on the electronic banking with the parameter value of 0.222, standard error of 0.076, t-value of 0.232 and significant level of 0.004.

The effect social influence has on the use of e-banking during the pandemic

Table 4.5 shows the effect social influence have on the use of e-banking during the pandemic. The item with the robust response rate was that “most people around them use e-banking,” with a weighted mean of 3.92 and a standard dev. of 0.96. The participants apparently recognised that “people who influence their behaviour thought that they should use e-banking” as the mean score for second item indicates, that participants agreed to the statement. Finally, respondents gave the statement that, “people who are important to us think that they should use e-banking,” a 3.52 mean (agreed) rating. In keeping with Accenture survey (2020), customers who had already been using e-banking prior to the pandemic found the service easier to use than those who were using it for the first time. However, the survey also realised that banks that provided easy-to-use digital platforms saw an increase in customer satisfaction during the pandemic.

The linear regression revealed that the perceived ease of use had positive impact on the electronic banking with the parameter value of 0.188, standard error of 0.066, t-value of 0.167 and significant level of 0.005.

Service quality and support during the pandemic

Table 4.7 reveals the service quality and support during the pandemic item with the highest response rate was that “network connections to e-banking platforms were generally good,” with a weighted mean of 3.20 and a standard deviation of 1.06. More so, the participants fairly agreed that support from the bank is readily available when faced with e-banking challenges (with a mean of 3.02 and standard deviation of 1.07). Finally, the participants were sceptical regarding the view that they found that the e-banking platform they use has a low turnaround time i.e., the time it takes to resolve challenges, receiving a 2.98 mean (indifferent) rating.

Consequently, this data suggest that the quality of e-banking services and customer support has become even more critical during the covid-19 outbreak. Banking sectors that have invested in their e-banking capabilities and customer support channels have been better able to serve their customers during covid-19. With some likely deviations attributable to the current challenging situation for covid-19, the results are similar to those of previous investigations (Haq and Awan, 2020; Shankar and Jebarajakirthy, 2019; Blut *et al.*, 2015). Privacy and security were shown to have little impact on the quality of service provided to customers, and hence, no middle ground was anticipated (Quach *et al.*, 2016). Thus, it is crucial that customers have a positive experience with support and service from the banks.

The linear regression revealed that the perceived ease of use had positive impact on the electronic banking with the parameter value of 0.016, standard error of 0.077, t-value of 0.011 and significant level of 0.837.

Price value - this includes the charge for using each e-banking service

Table 4.8 shows the price value (i.e., the charge for using each e-banking service) item with the highest response rate was that “at the current rate, using e-banking provided good value,” with a weighted mean of 3.73 and a standard deviation of 1.04. More so, the participants agreed that they found that e-banking is a good value for money (with a mean of 3.65 and standard deviation of

1.03). Finally, the participants were sceptical regarding the view that they found that e-banking is fairly priced, receiving a 3.21 mean (indifferent) rating. Consequently, this data affirmed that e-banking services offered good value and vice versa.

Support (Hedonic Motivation)

Table 4.9 shows the HM item with the highest response rate was that “participants found that using e-banking is enjoyable” with a weighted mean of 4.00 and a standard dev. of 0.99; while, the participants agreed that they found that using e-banking is entertaining (with a mean of 3.09 and standard deviation of 1.23). Consequently, this data affirmed that the HM of participants is centered on their drive to seek pleasure and avoid pain. It is an essential facet of human behaviour and one of the most influential theories of hedonic motivation is the hedonic treadmill theory (Mancini *et al.*, 2011), which advocates that people have a baseline level of happiness that they tend to return to after experiencing positive or negative events. This theory has been supported Brickman *et al.* (1978) classic research on lottery winners and accident victims, which acknowledged that both groups returned to their pre-event levels of happiness within a year.

Furthermore, another imperative characteristic of hedonic motivation is the role of dopamine, a neurotransmitter that is associated with pleasure and reward. Dopamine is released in response to pleasurable experiences, and its release is thought to reinforce behaviour that leads to these experiences (Mancini *et al.*, 2011). Thus, Knutson and Cooper (2005) argue that people who received a monetary reward for completing a task exhibited increased activity in the brain’s dopamine-rich ventral striatum.

The linear regression revealed that the perceived ease of use had positive impact on the electronic banking with the parameter value of 0.340, standard error of 0.095, t-value of 0.217 and significant level of 0.000.

Generally, the multiple linear regression analysis was found to be significant with 0.000 significant level, while the R-squared was found to be 75.2%. This shows that the multiple linear regression model was able to explain the variation in the response variable by 75.2%.

CONCLUSION

The study concludes that e-banking has proven to be an invaluable tool during the covid-19 outbreak, providing a safe and convenient way for customers to manage their finances. As the covid-19 continues, it is likely that e-banking will continue to play an essential role in the banking industry and other sectors and the participants apparently acknowledged that “learning to use e-banking requires little effort,” as seen in the result of the mean score. Overall, respondents gave the statement that, “it is easy for them to become skilful at using e-banking,” with a 3.95 mean (agreed) rating. Finally, customers who had already been using e-banking prior to the pandemic found the service easier to use than those who were using it for the first time. However, the survey also realised that banks that provided easy-to-use digital platforms saw an increase in customer satisfaction during the pandemic.

Recommendation

the study recommends the following to banks, bank workers, bank users that;

- 1) The E-banking channels should be advertised properly by Central Bank of Nigeria and other subsidiary banks to the public to ensure that both the literate and the illiterate can use them, to enable us be free from any shock of reoccurring COVID or any likes of it.
- 2) The general public should be responsive to the changes in the advancement of technology in bank related issues to avoid being taken unawares.
- 3) There should be establishment of banks in rural areas to make the elders and those primitive once have access to some of these innovations.

REFERENCES

- Hernández-Murillo, R. (2010). *Strategic Online-Banking Adoption*, Thompson publishers, India, 34.
- Ololade, B. and Ogbeide, S. (2017). E- Banking in Nigeria: Issues and Challenges. *Research Journal of Finance Account.*, 2(3), 10-25.
- Onodugo, I. C. (2015). Overview of electronic banking in Nigeria. *International Journal of Multidisciplinary*, 1(4), 1-15.
- Chiemeké, S. C. & Ewwiekpaefe, A. E. (2006). *The adoption of internet banking in Nigeria an empirical investigation*.
- Hosein, N. Z. (2009). Internet Banking: An Empirical Study of Adoption Rates Among Midwest Community Banks. *Journal of Business and Economics*, 7(11), 235-247, <https://doi.org/10.19030/jber.v7i11.2355>.
- Nitsure, R. R. (2003). E-Banking: Challenges and Opportunities. *Economics and Political*, 38, (51), 5377–5381.
- Yee-Loong, A., Chong, K., Ooi, Lin, B., & Tan, B. (2010). Online banking adoption: an empirical analysis. *International Journal of Bank Mark*, 28(4), 267–287, <https://doi.org/10.1108/02652321011054963>.
- Davis, F. D., Bagozzi, R. P. & Warshaw, P. R. (1989). User Acceptance of Computer Technology: A Comparison of Two Theoretical Models. *Management. Science Journal*, 35(8), 982–1003, <https://doi.org/10.1287/mnsc.35.8.982>.
- El-Qirem, I. A. (2013). Critical Factors Influencing E-Banking Service Adoption in Jordanian Commercial Banks: A Proposed Model. *International Journal of Business Res.*, 6(3), 217-229, <https://doi.org/10.5539/ibr.v6n3p229>.
- Al-Tarawneh, J. M. (2016). Factors Influencing the adoption of Mobile banking services in Jordan from the perspective of customers. *Overview and Pilot study*, 6(9), 8-19.
- Venkatesh, M. & Davis, D. (2003). User Acceptance of Information Technology: Toward a Unified View," *Marketing Journal Internal Services* 27(3), 425-435, <https://doi.org/10.2307/30036540>.
- Tam, C., Santos, D., & Oliveira, T. (2020). Exploring the influential factors of continuance intention to use mobile Apps: Extending the expectation confirmation model. *Information System Front*, 22(1), 243–257, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10796-018-9864-5>.
- Rahi, S., Ghani, M. A., Alnaser, F. M. & Ngah, A. H. (2018). Investigating the role of unified theory of acceptance and use of technology (UTAUT) in internet banking adoption context. *Management. Science Letter*, 2(3), 173–186, <https://doi.org/10.5267/j.msl.2018.1.001>.

- Tan, K. S., Chong, S. C., Loh, L. P. & Lin, B. (2010). An evaluation of e-banking and m-banking adoption factors and preference in Malaysia: a case study. *International Journal of Mobile Communication*, 8(5), 489-507, <https://doi.org/10.1504/ijmc.2010.034935>.
- Michael, V. (2019). Mobile Banking Adoption: An Exploration of The Behavioural Intention of Consumers in Ireland. *Journal of Accounting Finance*, 19(8), 15-21, <https://doi.org/10.33423/jaf.v19i8.2614>.
- Sánchez-Torres, J. A., Canada, F. J. A., Sandoval, A. V. & J.-A. S. Alzate, J. A. S. (2016). E-banking in Colombia: factors favouring its acceptance, online trust and government support. *International Journal of Bank Mark.*, 36(1), 170–183, <https://doi.org/10.1108/ijbm-10-2016-0145>.
- Asiyanbi, H. B. & Ishola, A. A. (2018). E-banking services impact and customer satisfaction in selected bank branches in Ibadan metropolis, Oyo state, Nigeria. *Accounting Journal*, 2(1), 153–160, <https://doi.org/10.5267/j.ac.2018.3.001>.
- Mwiya, B., Chikumbi, F., Shikaputo, C., Kabala, E., Kaulung'ombe, B. & Siachinji, B. (2017). Examining Factors Influencing E-Banking Adoption: Evidence from Bank Customers in Zambia. *America Journal of Industrial Business Management*, 7(6), 741–759, <https://doi.org/10.4236/ajibm.2017.76053>.
- Sinha. I., & Mukherjee, S. (2016). Acceptance of technology, related factors in use of off branch e-banking: an Indian case study. *Journal of High Technology Management*, 27(1), 88–100, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.hitech.2016.04.008>.
- Yu, C. S. & Asgarkhani, M. (2015). An investigation of trust in e-banking: Evidence from Taiwan and New Zealand empirical studies. *Management Research*, 38(12), 1267–1284, <https://doi.org/10.1108/MRR-09-2014-0210>.
- Nasri, W. & Charfeddine, L. (2012). Factors affecting the adoption of Internet banking in Tunisia: An integration theory of acceptance model and theory of planned behaviour. *Journal of High Technology Management Research*, 23(1), 1–14, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.hitech.2012.03.001>.
- Hanafizadeh, H. & Khedmatgozar, H. K. (2012). The mediating role of the dimensions of the perceived risk in the effect of customers' awareness on the adoption of Internet banking in Iran," *Electron. Journal of Commercial Research*, 12(2), 151–175, May 2012, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10660-012-9090-z>.
- Foon, Y. S. & Chan, B. (2012). Internet Banking Adoption in Kuala Lumpur: An Application of UTAUT Model. *International Journal of Business Management*, 6(4), 161-174, <https://doi.org/10.5539/ijbm.v6n4p161>.
- Sundarraaj, R. P. & Manochehri, N. (2011). Application of an Extended TAM Model for Online Banking Adoption: A Study at a Gulf-region University. *Journal of Management Science*, 24(1), 1–13, <https://doi.org/10.4018/irmj.2011010101>.

- Riquelme, H. E. & Rios, R. E. (2010). The moderating effect of gender in the adoption of mobile banking. *International Journal of Banking and Finance*, 28(5), 328–341, <https://doi.org/10.1108/02652321011064872>.
- Indrasari, A., Nadjmie, N. & Endri, E. (2022). Determinants of satisfaction and loyalty of e-banking users during the COVID-19 pandemic. *International Journal of Data Network Science*, 6(2), 497–508, <https://doi.org/10.5267/j.ijdns.2021.12.004>.
- Al-Hajri, S., Echchabi, A., Ghayas, S. & Akour, M. A. (2022). Customers' Acceptance of E-banking During the COVID-19 Pandemic: The Case of Oman. *Contemporary Research in Accounting and Finance*, 2(4), 237–251, https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-16-8267-4_10.
- Salam, M., Saha, T., Rahman, M. H. & Mutsuddi, P. (2021). Challenges to Mobile Banking Adaptation in COVID-19 Pandemic. *Journal of Business Management Sciences*, 9(2), 101–113, <https://doi.org/10.12691/jbms-9-3-2>.
- Shahabi, V., Azar, A., Faezy-Razi, F. & M. Fallah, M. F. (2020). Simulation of the effect of COVID-19 outbreak on the development of branchless banking in Iran: case study of Resalat Qard–al-Hasan Bank. *Revolutionary Finance Journal*, 13(1), 85–108, <https://doi.org/10.1108/rbf-06-2020-0123>.
- Nga, T. T. T. (2022). Factors affecting Intention to Use E-banking Services in the Context of the COVID-19 Pandemic - A Case Study in Ho Chi Minh City, Vietnam. *Webology*, 19(1), 1573–1586, <https://doi.org/10.14704/web/v19i1/web19105>.
- Al-Qeisi, K. & Al-Abdallah, G. (2014). Website Design and Usage Behaviour: An Application of the UTAUT Model for Internet Banking in UK. *International Journal of Marketing Studies*, 6(2), 241–258, <https://doi.org/10.5539/ijms.v6n1p75>.
- Ul-Haq, I. & Awan, T. M. (2020). Impact of e-banking service quality on e-loyalty in pandemic times through interplay of e-satisfaction. *Vilakshan - XIMB Journal of Management* 17(1), 39–55, <https://doi.org/10.1108/XJM-07-2020-0039>.
- Shankar, A. & Jebarajakirthy, C. (2019). The influence of e-banking service quality on customer loyalty: A moderated mediation approach. *International Journal of Bank Marketing*, 37(5), 1119–1142.
- Blut, M., Frennea, C. M., Mittal, V. & Mothersbaugh, D. L. (2015). How procedural, financial and relational switching costs affect customer satisfaction, repurchase intentions, and repurchase behavior: A meta-analysis. *International Journal of Research in Marketing*, 32(2), 226–229.
- Quach, T.N., Thaichon, P. & Jebarajakirthy, C. (2016). Internet service providers' service quality and its effect on customer loyalty of different usage patterns. *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, 29(4), 104–113.

- Mancini, A.D., Bonanno, G. A. & Clark, A.E. (2011). Stepping off the hedonic treadmill. *Journal of Individual Differences*, 32(3). [Online] Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1027/1614-0001/a000047>.
- Brickman, P., Coates, D. and Janoff-Bulman, R. (1978). Lottery winners and accident victims: Is happiness relative? *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 36(8), pp.917-927.
- Knutson, B. & Cooper, J. C. (2005). Functional magnetic resonance imaging of reward prediction. *Current Opinion in Neurology*, 18(4), 411-417.
- Kaiser, H. F. (1970). A second-generation little jiffy. *Psychometrika*, 35(4), 401-415.
- Hair, J. F., Black, W. C., Babin, B. J. & Anderson, R. E. (2014). *Multivariate data analysis (7th ed.)*. Pearson Education Limited.
- Fabrigar, L. R., Wegener, D. T., MacCallum, R. C. & Strahan, E. J. (1999). Evaluating the use of exploratory factor analysis in psychological research. *Psychological Methods*, 4(3), 272-299.
- Tabachnick, B. G. and Fidell, L. S. (2007). *Using multivariate statistics (5th ed.)*. Pearson Education.
- Kline, R. B. (2015). *Principles and practice of structural equation modeling (4th ed.)*. The Guilford Press.
- Salehi, A. (2022). Assessing the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on the banking system performance: Evidence from the Canadian banking industry. *International Journal of Finance & Banking Studies*, 11(4), 1-16.
- Chavda, V. (2021). Effectiveness of e-banking during COVID-19 pandemic. *International Journal of Advanced Research in Computer and Communication Engineering*, 10(10), 1-8.
- Okunbanjo, O. I. (2021). E-banking and emergent of COVID-19 in Lagos State. Paper presented at the annual conference of Faculty of Management Sciences.
- Okafor, C. A. (2021). E-banking and entrepreneurial development in Nigeria. *International Journal of Business & Law Research*, 9(1), 79-88.
- Ahmed, A. A., Buhari, M. A. & Abba, A. A. (2021). Impact and adoption of mobile banking on the Nigerian customers in a COVID-19 pandemic era (A Case Study of Kano State Metropolis). *Dutse Journal of Pure and Applied Sciences*, 7(1), 204-210.
- Kaushik, R., Rastogi, P. & Vakeel, S. (2020). A study on the effect of COVID pandemic on e-banking services adoption. *Turkish Journal of Computer and Mathematics Education*, 11(2), 650- 660.